

CBDRx Growth Protocol

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CBDRx plants were grown indoors at 20-25C and 55-70% humidity under a mixture of fluorescent T-5 lamps and 1100W High Pressure Sodium Lamps manufactured by PL Lights. We made clonal cuttings approximately 10cm in height that included stems and leaves. These were immediately transferred to 42mm coconut coir plugs for rooting, then a coconut and perlite blend once roots were observed, where they remained for 40 days. Plants were then transferred to soil in 10cm pots for for 4 weeks of vegetative growth. Rooting and vegetative growth conditions included an 18:6 hour light:dark cycle and water as needed. Plants were transferred to 20L pots 10 weeks of flowering conditions using a 12:12 our light:dark cycle. Plants were fertilized with a micronutrient blend certified by the Organic Materials Review Institute plus biochar. Under flowering conditions, plants were watered every 7-9 days.